

METROLOGICAL SUPPORT OF TECHNICAL REGULATION IN PRODUCTION

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Abstract. Implement metrological services in our country today transparent, simplified interactive procedures are properly organized not done, including calibration of industrial sectors and social. There is no metrological supply system in the field causing problems. In particular, the private sector in the field low share, modernization of metrological laboratories, metrological support in industrial sectors and social sectors does not allow improvement. Regarding metrology up to the new revision the state of our current legislation, the experience of foreign countries and analysis of existing national metrology systems, by them suggestions and recommendations to improve this law caused the necessity. 1993 Law on Metrology It was accepted in today's content and metrology non-compliance with internationally recognized documents in the field and the results of measurements and tests carried out in the republic abroad showed that it does not ensure recognition.

Keywords: Second, newly revised, systematically, scientific, participation, development.

МЕТРОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ТЕХНИЧЕСКОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ

Аннотация. Внедрения метрологических служб в нашей стране сегодня прозрачных, упрощенных интерактивных процедур должным образом не организовано, в том числе калибровки промышленных отраслей и соц. В области отсутствует система метрологического обеспечения, что вызывает проблемы. В частности, низкая доля частного сектора в сфере, модернизация метрологических лабораторий, метрологическое обеспечение в промышленных отраслях и социальной сфере не позволяют улучшить ситуацию. В отношении метрологии до новой редакции состояние нашего действующего законодательства, опыт зарубежных стран и анализ существующих национальных систем метрологии, их предложения и рекомендации по совершенствованию этого закона вызвали необходимость. 1993 г. Закон о метрологии был принят в сегодняшнем содержании и несоответствии метрологии международно признанным документам в данной области и результаты измерений и испытаний, проведенных в республике за рубежом, показали, что он не обеспечивает признания.

Ключевые слова: Второй, вновь пересмотренный, системный, научный, участие, разработка.

Establishing a metrology service in our republic and physical and participation of legal entities, their functions in this regard detailed information on their responsibilities is given in this law.

- Chapter 5 of this newly revised Law on Metrology, i.e General rules;
- Regulation of the field of activity related to metrology;
- Organization of activities related to metrology;
- State metrology inspection and control;

The final regulations consist of chapters and include 32 articles received. The legal bases of metrology in our country strengthening, developing it based on modern requirements and that aimed at determining the priority task in the future.

Firstly, entities operating in the field of metrology as the Cabinet of Ministers, state bodies and legal entities the powers of metrology services in this area have been strengthened.

Secondly, public-private on calibration of measuring instruments that metrology services can be organized on the basis of partnership defined.

Thirdly, to accelerate the introduction of high technologies into the industry and their it is possible to carry out the work of systematically ensuring its accuracy circles are extended.

Fourth, in the implementation of metrological inspection comparison, calibration, measurements of used measuring instruments implementation and test tool attestation methods are included.

Fifth, in order to harmonize with the rules of international documents the new term "packaged goods" was introduced, state metrology inspection and control with a new object called —packaged goods, as well as state metrology control over their quantity in packaging and sale filled with a new regulatory substance.

Sixth, state metrological inspection and metrological control in what circumstances, in what form, by whom a separate norm is established. Seventh, other not involved in measurement and testing specific criteria for metrological inspection of technical means is set.

In this law, to the National Institute of Metrology of Uzbekistan, measurements powers aimed at ensuring unity are defined:

- The base of national standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan improves and ensures development;
- maintaining benchmarks and measuring instruments of the highest accuracy standing and comparing them at the international level, as well as performs work on storage and transfer of units of magnitude;
- regulations on ensuring that measurements are in a single unit develops draft documents;
- on mutual recognition of metrology inspection results participates in the implementation of international agreements;
- metrology inspection and scientific in the field of metrology activities conducts research.

At the same time, in the implementation of metrology activities in the Law increase the share of the private sector, investment projects in the field wider involvement, provision of quality metrological services to the population filled with norms defining the basis of provision. This Law regulates the field of metrology based on international principles development, protection of life and health of citizens, protection of the environment, animal and plant life, in addition, the state used for the purpose of ensuring defense and security a citizen who is interested in impartial, reliable and comparable results of measurement, help meet the needs of society and the state. Steam gasoline, obtained from the top of the atmospheric column, condenses, cools and enters the separator. To create an acute irrigation, the top of the Atmospheric column is supplied from this separator with traganaya phase - gasoline. The gasoline surplus from the irrigation is sent, together

with the gasoline from the pre-evaporation column, for further processing. And the fractional price of the autonomous process for the growing time

For the input of side fractions of the columns (kerosene, light and heavy diesel fuel), the corresponding stripping columns are used. In each of the tripping, in order to improve the quality of the input fractions, superheated steam is supplied as an evaporating agent. It has the same parameters as with the ego submission of Andes Atmospheric Column. For stripping from the composition of the side strips of light fractions, a supply of an evaporating agent is provided to all stripping columns. From the atmospheric column, kerosene enters the vertical stripping.

Here, light fractions are stripped back to the column, and the stripped fuel from the bottom of the stripping is pumped to further scaling, water washing and dehydration. It is allowed to obtain fuel without scaling and water washing, provided that its quality complies with the requirements of the current standard.

Light and heavy diesel fuel and extra-strong from the atmospheric column, respectively, into medium and low stripping. Steamed light fractions also return to the atmosphere column. From the bottom of the stripper, fuel is taken by the pump and pumped through the heat exchanger to the intermediate factory park.

The consumption of superheated steam supplied to the column as an evaporating agent, varies from 1.2 to 3.5% of the mass. to the original sire. The use of a traditional pairing agent - superheated water vapor during the distillation of cheese is associated with such negative phenomena as an increase in energy costs (in the heat and cold) and distillation and condensation; increase in the load of the columns in pairs, which leads to an increase in the diameter of the apparatus and the loss of liquid between the board; water vapor and ego condensate, as outside agents, together with hydrocarbons in the apparatus, occupy their usable space, And thereby reduce the efficiency of the process, as well as the productivity of heat and mass transfer and auxiliary equipment; more natural than petroleum products requires a thorough follow-up of their dry; The production of superheated water vapor requires significant energy and technological costs [1–5]. And in connection with this, the development of an effective technology for the distillation of liquid hydrogen mixtures by replacing superheated water vapor with an alternative evaporating agent (hydrocarbon vapors) is, at the present time, an actual scientific and technical problem.

The introduction of high-precision instruments that meet metrological IT is not necessary to use the method of requirements, which is not based on the use of gasoline vapor as an evaporating agent instead of water vapor, contributes to the intensification of the process of refining liquid hydrocarbons. This technology, along with the suppression of the above negative phenomena, also has the following advantages: the possibility of oil product penetration is excluded, which is especially important for aviation kerosene and diesel fuel; the flow of circulating water and electricity to the air-cooling apparatus is reduced, as well as the required capacity of the condensers due to the absence of water vapor in the condensing steam of oil products; increases the efficiency of regeneration of the heat of the product of atmospheric distillation of the gully bucket in the heat exchange apparatus and the resulting increase in the general thermal regime retification column; sorrosion apparatus is decreasing, especially condensers and pipelines; The overall Reliable Operation of Primary Distillation of Oil and Gas Condensate Blends is on the rise. Positive effects san also be achieved in metrological assurance of the accuracy of regulation of technological parameters. Note the basic theoretical and

experimental research, together with specialists from Fergana and Bukhara oil refineries, basic scientific new technologies created -sukhoy distillation of liquid gulvovorodornykh mixtures. In the conditions of the Fergana Oil Refinery, the annual economic effect is strong and will show you how to apply the technology. It cost sea than 2.5 billion sums.

The quality of the manufactured product is set to its own standard level should be answered. This is the quality of the product being evaluated the values of the indicators are the base values of the corresponding indicators is a relative specification of product quality based on comparison with Technical level of the product, quality indicators of the product relies on the competitiveness and technicality of the evaluated product match the values of the indicators describing the improvement based on the comparison with the base values of the indicators, the product is a relative detail of quality.

Product quality assurance is set to the standard is to ensure the numerical value of its indicators. Product quality indicator of one or several properties that are part of the product quality Quantitative description, its creation and use is specific in consumption It is said that the construction is applied to the conditions. Relative evaluation of the scientific and technical level of the regulatory document

Details of the required quality indicators include: Task indicators - the main tasks that he must perform the teller describes the properties of the product and the field of application defines. Task indicators are divided into three subgroups: task and technical efficiency indicators; construction indicators; content and structural indicators.

Accuracy indicators are divided into groups according to:

- Persistence - the object is known for a certain period of time maintaining its capacity continuously during the period of performance of the volume of work describes the feature.

- Endurance - defined maintenance of the facility and its ability to work until it becomes unusable in the repair system describes the storage feature.

- Repairability - to prevent damage to the object and to determine the causes of failure and repair and maintenance to eliminate the consequences of the violation by showing describes the compatibility features.

- Maintainability - the state of order and workability of the object and keeping the product in good condition during and after storage and storage after transportation describes the feature.

Indicators of saving resources - raw ash of the product, labor in the use (consumption) of materials, fuel, energy reflect its technical perfection in terms of resource requirements describes its properties. Resource saving indicators are divided into three subgroups:

- Economical use of raw materials and materials indicators

- As indicators of efficient use of energy, usually, from comparative indicators, i.e. energy consumption and the product produced or the useful work performed the ratio to the size (unit of work) is used.

- From raw food, materials, fuel, energy and labor resources summarized indicators describing economical use as product development, production and use (consumption the use of indicators describing expenses in making). possible

Ergonomic indicators —man-thing (including —man-machine) describes the system and the hygienic, taking into account a set of anthropometric, physiological and psychological characteristics takes

Aesthetic indicators are the meaning of information, the acceptability of the form, characterized by the perfection of the structure and perfect preparation.

Technological - the composition and structure of the product in the production, use and quality indicators of its construction, of expenses in restoring conditions of production and performance of works describes the properties that can ensure the minimum. Suitability for transportation - the product can be moved (transported) in an open place, that is, related to the use (consumption) of the product, not describes adaptation to actions.

Indicators of standardization and unification standard, integrated and original components of the product it is enriched with, as well as the level of identification with other items. Patent-legal indications are the technique used in the product the degree of renewal of solutions, with their patent that it is protected, as well as without barriers to purchase within the country and abroad describes the ability to put.

Environmental indicators are consumption when using the product the level of harmful effects on the environment describes. The environment in the selection and determination of these indicators protection requirements are taken into account.

Safety indicators are mainly by product type formed, to the human life in the use and consumption of the product, health and property, environmental safety features and describes the characteristics. Hence, the product specifications specified in the product standards a set of requirements and a set of requirements for product quality constitutes, with required quality indicators and standardization is provided.

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